

Relation between partition coefficient of a weak organic base and properties of solvents

Manisha A. Agrawal, Jeena Harjit and Rama Pande*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010, India

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Some physical parameters of *N*-phenyl-2-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid, viz. partition coefficients in various organic solvent-aqueous systems, density, molar volume, solubility parameters, primary medium activity coefficients, free energy of transfer of a solute in solvent and values of $1000 \rho/M$, have been determined. The partition data are discussed on the basis of Regular Solution Theory. An attempt is made to correlate the values of K_D for a number of common organic solvents, with some physical parameter characteristics of the solvents.

A versatile organic reagent *N*-phenyl-2-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid acts as weak organic base in presence of strong acidic solutions. Compound with hydroxamic acid as functional group are often isolated from naturally occurring substances and these reagents as product of some photochemical reactions are recognised. Although they have wide ranging applications in various fields¹, their physicochemical properties have received little attention². In chelate extraction systems, inert solvents are mostly used. In the present investigation, the relationship between the partition data of this reagent and the physical properties of various organic solvents has been described.

Results and Discussion

The values of various physical parameters determined for *N*-phenyl-2-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid are reported in Table 1. These parameters are, the partition coefficient (K_D) between water and water-immiscible common organic solvents, density (ρ), molar volume (V_1), solubility parameter (δ_c) values, free energy of transfer of solute (ΔG_t^\ddagger) in solvents and values of primary medium activity coefficient (γ_1). The reagent is sparingly soluble in water but freely soluble in common organic solvents. K_D values

are calculated following the equation,

$$K_D = \frac{C_2}{C_1} \quad (1)$$

where C_2 and C_1 are the concentrations of hydroxamic acid in the organic and aqueous phases respectively. The data reported here are the average of at least six separate determinations. K_D values can be regarded as the distribution constants for the monomeric form of this reagent, as there is no significant variation in K_D involved with total reagent concentration.

Values of K_D can be correlated with regular solution theory. A regular solution is defined as, 'one which has no chemical interaction between solute and solvent molecules and no change in states of association and orientation by mixing'. To such solutions, Hildebrand's theory of regular solution³ can be applied according to which the K_D values can be related directly to the right-hand-side terms of equation (2), when the concentration of the solute is sufficiently low in both the phases,

$$\ln \frac{\phi_{1,org}}{\phi_{1,aq}} = \frac{V_1}{RT} [(\delta_c - \delta_{aq})^2 - (\delta_c - \delta_{org})^2] + V_1 \left[\frac{1}{V_{org}} - \frac{1}{V_{aq}} \right] \quad (2)$$

Table 1. Physical constants of *N*-phenyl-2-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid*

Solvent	Solvents type	K_D	δ	δ_c	$\gamma_1 \times 10^3$	$\Delta G_t^\ddagger \times 10^3$
Benzene	Ar-NHB-HBA	12.00 ± 0.058	9.15	15.00	5.87	-1.50
Carbontetrachloride	NHB	3.02 ± 0.028	8.6	14.94	26.71	-0.70
Chlorobenzene	Ar-NHB-HBA	13.05 ± 0.012	9.5	15.10	2.84	-1.55
Chloroform	NHB-HBD	24.30 ± 0.032	9.3	14.99	3.68	-1.92
Cyclohexane	NHB	1.29 ± 0.043	8.2	14.86	76.70	-0.15
1,2-Dichlorobenzene	-	6.80 ± 0.055	10.0	15.38	1.54	-1.15
1,2-Dichloroethane	NHB	52.43 ± 0.050	9.8	15.07	1.14	-2.38
n-Hexane	NHB	1.00 ± 0.071	7.3	14.46	442.86	-0.003
Toluene	Ar-NHB-HBA	6.92 ± 0.031	8.9	14.93	10.10	-1.16

* K_D = Partition coefficient; δ_c = solubility parameter of solute in $\text{cal}^{1/2} \text{ml}^{-1/2}$; NHB = non-hydrogen bonding solvent; HBD = hydrogen bond donar; HBA = hydrogen bond acceptor.

where, ϕ_1 is the volume fraction of the solute, V_1 the molar volume of the solute, δ_C the solubility parameter of the solute, δ_{aq} the solubility parameter of the aqueous phase, δ_{org} the solubility parameter of the organic solvent, V_{org} the molar volume of the organic solvent and V_{aq} the molar volume of the aqueous phase. The δ_C values of *N*-phenyl-2-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid were calculated following equation (2) considering the δ value of water as 23.4 cal^{1/2} ml^{-1/2}, and for various organic solvents, δ were obtained from literature³.

The data on solubility parameters (Table 1) show that the calculated values of δ_C for the solvents investigated are reasonably constant. This indicates that properties of hydroxamic acid solutions in these solvents are at least qualitatively similar to those postulated for regular solutions. Although the quantitative application of these equations is difficult because of the dependence on factors involving small differences between relatively closely matched solubility parameters, but to apply the approach qualitatively, consideration of solubility parameter as an important factor in the evaluation of organic solvents for extraction, can be quite useful. The knowledge of solubility parameter values (δ_C) will prove fruitful not only in choosing proper solvent for extraction but also in extending the range of extraction method as well.

The free energy of transfer (ΔG_T^\ddagger) of non-electrolyte may also be obtained from the distribution of a solute between two immiscible solvents, if the partition coefficient of the solute is defined as C_2/C_1 , then,

$$\Delta G_T^\ddagger = -RT \ln \frac{C_2}{C_1} \quad (3)$$

The ΔG_T^\ddagger values thus calculated at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ for this reagent are presented in Table 1.

It was also shown that the primary medium activity coefficient of non-electrolyte solute (i) can be calculated following the equation,

$$RT \ln \gamma_i = V_1 (\delta_i - \delta)^2 \quad (4)$$

where V_1 and δ_i are the molar volume and solubility parameter of the solute respectively. Table 1 lists the values of γ_i for *N*-phenyl-2-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid.

In solvent extraction systems, if we know the fundamental parameters of the solvent, the solution and the solute, we shall be able to pre-estimate the behaviour of solute and moreover, the role of solvent and/or diluent.

Experimental

N-Phenyl-2-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid was prepared according to the reported procedure⁵ and purified by crystallisation from benzene. All the organic solvents and

hydrochloric acid used were of analytical grade. Saturated solution of ammonium metavanadate was prepared in glass-distilled water. Chloroform was shaken six times with equal volumes of water to remove ethanol and then distilled.

A Carl-Zeiss-Jena Spekol EK-1 spectrophotometer was used.

Partition coefficient (K_D) : For the measurement of K_D an aliquot of a solution of hydroxamic acid (~50 mg) in organic solvent (10–15 ml) and an equal volume of water (pH 7) were shaken manually for 0.5 h. After centrifugation, the phases were separated and the concentration of the reagent in each phase was determined spectrophotometrically using vanadium(v) method⁶. An aliquot of the solution phase was taken in chloroform (10 ml). Concentrated HCl (to adjust the acidity in the range 4–7 mol dm⁻³) and aqueous saturated solution of ammonium metavanadate (5 ml) were added to it. The resulting coloured complex was extracted in the organic phase. The extract after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate was made up to 25 ml and its absorbance measured at 520 nm against chloroform as blank. The concentration was then computed from the calibration curve.

Density measurement : Hydrostatic weighing method was used for the measurement of density of *N*-phenyl-2-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid. Repeated weighings were performed to record the accurate results. All the weighings were corrected for air buoyancy. The density was calculated using the formula,

$$D_{HA} = \frac{W_{air}}{W_{air} - W_{water}} (D_{water} - D_{air}) + D_{air}$$

where, D_{HA} is the density of hydroxamic acid, D_{water} the density of water, D_{air} the density of air, W_{air} the weight of sample in air and W_{water} the weight of sample in water.

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